

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODS AND EFFECTIVE TECHNOLOGIES.

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Abstract. Today, the introduction of interactive methods into the educational process is considered one of the important factors in increasing the effectiveness of training. Interactive methods serve to establish effective communication between the teacher and the student, placing the active participation of students and pupils at the center of training. The implementation of these methods mainly involves the active assimilation of educational material by students, the development of independent thinking skills, and the strengthening of practical cognitive abilities.

Key Words: interactive methods, language teaching, ICT, critical thinking, collaboration, didactic goal, experiential learning.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of interactive methods in teaching English represents a progressive shift from traditional, teacher-centered methodologies to a student-centered approach. In an era where communication, collaboration, and creativity are essential, these interactive techniques enhance the learning experience by actively engaging students in the educational process. Interactive learning techniques allow students to participate more effectively, enabling them to apply their knowledge in practical, real-life situations.

This article investigates the role of interactive methods in English teaching, focusing on their principles, effectiveness, and the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in facilitating these methods. The main objectives are to explore

how these strategies enhance student involvement, promote communication skills, and encourage critical thinking.

METHODS

The use of interactive methods in the educational process is based on several principles. Including:

Student engagement and participation: Interactive methods ensure that students are active participants in the learning process rather than passive observers. This approach makes learning interesting and dynamic, and increases students' interest and motivation. The importance of interactive approaches in modern education has been emphasized in many studies. For example, Johnson and Johnson note ¹that interactive learning can improve collaboration among students and develop their social skills. At the same time ², Vygotsky's social learning theory emphasizes that interactive activities help accelerate the process of knowledge sharing among students.

Interactive methods not only effectively organize the learning process, but also stimulate students to develop problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and creativity. Teamwork, role- playing, and discussions used in lessons develop students' communication skills and create an atmosphere of mutual trust between them. For example, Bonwell and Eison described ³active learning methods and emphasized the importance of these methods in increasing student engagement.

Interactive methods also develop students' personal responsibility and encourage them to learn independently. The effectiveness of these methods is especially evident in their adaptation to the needs of students at different levels ⁴. As a result, interactive approaches not only provide knowledge, but also promote personal development.

¹Johnson, D. W. and Johnson, R. T. (1999). Learning Together and Alone: Cooperative, Competitive, and Individualized Learning (5th ed.). Allyn & Bacon.

²Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Mental Processes. Harvard University Press.

³ Bonwell, K. K. & Eison, J. A. (1991). Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1.

⁴Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. Journal of Engineering Education, 93(3), 223-231.

Therefore, the widespread use of interactive methods in the educational process is a necessary tool for maximum student involvement.

Collaboration and communication: Developing group and teamwork in the educational process, creating an environment based on the exchange of ideas and cooperation between students is one of the main principles of interactive methods. This approach helps students not only gain knowledge but also develop social skills. For example, ⁵Slavin's research emphasized the importance of collaborative learning to improve the quality of education and motivate students.

In interactive classes, students express themselves freely and exchange ideas with others through group discussions, projects, and team assignments. This not only expands students' knowledge but also develops their communication skills. Mercer's research ⁶has shown that collaborative communication among students helps deepen their learning and develop critical thinking skills.

At the same time, group activities allow students to learn from each other and accept different points of view. According to Vygotsky's social learning theory, personal growth and learning processes are accelerated through interaction with others. This theoretical framework supports the importance of increasing student engagement and creating a collaborative environment.

Thus, the principles of interactive methods based on the development of cooperation and communication not only increase the effectiveness of the educational process, but also serve to strengthen social ties between students. This allows us to consider education not only as a process of obtaining knowledge, but also as a broader environment of interaction.

Orientation to the didactic goal : the use of interactive methods ensures the achievement of educational goals and should be carefully planned by teachers. This approach ensures the purposefulness of the lesson process and helps to organize

⁵ Slavin , R. E. (1995). Cooperative Learning: Theory, Research, and Practice. Allyn and Bacon.

⁶Mercer, N. (2000). Words and Mind: How We Use Language to Think Together. Routledge.

meaningful and effective learning activities for students. Clark ⁷argues that any interactive activity should be based on specific pedagogical strategies to achieve the goal.

To successfully use interactive methods in the classroom, it is important that they are organized in a way that matches the purpose of the lesson, the content of the topic, and the needs of the students. For example, ⁸creating a lesson plan based on Bloom's taxonomy of learning objectives allows you to purposefully select interactive activities to develop students' knowledge, understanding, and application skills.

At the same time, organizing interactive lessons in an interesting and creative way encourages students to actively participate in the lesson process. Keller's ⁹ARCS model suggests that the interestingness of the content is one of the important factors in increasing motivation in education. According to this approach, interactive lessons should be meaningful and dynamic in order to attract students' attention and maintain their interest.

Thus, interactive methods aimed at achieving didactic goals increase the effectiveness of the educational process, enhance students' motivation, and promote a deeper understanding of the subject. This requires the teacher to plan activities based on specific goals and a creative approach to them.

Use of ICT: Use of ICT: Modern technologies, particularly online platforms and interactive programs, play an important role in the effective implementation of interactive methods. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) bring new possibilities to the educational process by creating an interesting and dynamic learning environment for students. The TPCK (Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge) model developed by Mishra and Koehler ¹⁰emphasizes the importance of

⁷Clark, D. H. (2001). Lessons from the past: Using instructional strategies in educational technology. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 30(2), 189-205.

⁸Bloom, B. S. (1956). *A Taxonomy of Educational Objectives: A Classification of Educational Goals*. Longmans.

⁹Keller, J. M. (1987). Development and use of the ARCS model of instructional design. *Journal of Instructional Development*, 10(3), 2-10.

¹⁰Mishra, P. and Koehler, M.J. (2006). Knowledge of technological pedagogical content: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017-1054

successfully integrating technology in education as it further enriches the pedagogical approach.

For example, platforms like Mentimeter or Kahoot allow students to assess their knowledge in an interactive and fun way. With these platforms, students are actively involved in answering questions or solving problems in real time. This not only activates the learning process but also helps to attract students' attention. Mayer's multimedia-based learning theory shows the role of technology in enhancing the learning process because its proper use helps integrate visual and auditory information into the students' minds.

Interactive programs can also help to establish effective communication and strengthen cooperation between teachers and students. In this process, Vaughan and Harrison's blended learning concept ¹¹ confirms the effectiveness of combining face-to-face and online teaching methods. Thus, the use of ICT not only enriches interactive methods, but also helps develop students' creativity and independent thinking skills.

To successfully implement interactive methods into the educational process, teachers need to focus on the following principles:

- **Experiential learning:** Interactive lessons that include hands-on activities help develop students' real-life problem-solving skills. As Dewey noted ¹², focusing on the practical aspects of education can encourage students to think for themselves, analyze problems, and find creative solutions. The experiential approach prepares students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice and develop skills needed for their future careers. For example, through role-playing, lab work, or problem-solving projects, students are given the opportunity to experience real-life situations they will encounter. Kolb's experiential learning model emphasizes engaging students in active learning and testing their acquired knowledge. According to this model, students gain a deeper understanding of knowledge through their own experiences and are prepared

¹¹Vaughan, N. and Harrison, D. R. (2005). Blended learning in higher education: Framework, principles and guidelines. Jossey - Bass .

¹²Dewey, J. (1938). Experience and Education. Macmillan.

to successfully complete new tasks. Hands-on activities also develop students' communication, teamwork, and critical thinking skills. For example, problem-solving assignments not only add life to the learning process but also allow students to demonstrate their ability to participate actively. Experiential learning is thus seen as an important component in enhancing the effectiveness of education;

- **Flexibility:** Organizing lessons according to the needs and characteristics of each student increases the effectiveness of interactive methods. Using a differentiated approach, teachers can take into account the individual pace of learning, interests, and level of knowledge of students (Tomlinson, 2001). This makes the learning process more interesting and effective. An adaptive approach aims to meet the learning needs of students while taking into account their individual differences. For example, some students learn better with visual materials, while others are more auditory or kinesthetic. Organizing a lesson with these characteristics in mind increases student motivation and engagement in the lesson. Flexible methods also make it possible to offer tasks and resources that are appropriate for students' different levels of proficiency. For example, beginner-level students can be given simpler tasks, while advanced students can be given more complex and analytical tasks. This not only engages each student in the process, but also creates conditions for them to fully demonstrate their potential. In addition, active communication between the teacher and students during the lesson and receiving feedback from them contributes to the effectiveness of interactive methods. This process allows for rethinking the lesson according to the needs of each student or changing strategies to achieve the expected results. Therefore, flexibility is an integral part of interactive methods;

- **Analytical Approach:** When using interactive methods, students should be guided to think critically and encouraged to evaluate their own results. By developing critical thinking, students can not only expand their knowledge but also learn to analyze available information and draw conclusions based on it. This approach helps students become conscious and active participants as they do not just accept ready-made information but also delve deeper into the data and apply it in practice. One of

the main aspects of the analytical approach is encouraging students to justify their opinions and develop arguments. For example, involving students in a discussion of a problem encourages them to confidently express their opinions and make decisions based on evidence. This process allows students to master logical thinking and an analytical approach, which will help them solve various problems in the future. In addition, the process of assessing and checking students' own achievements helps students actively participate in the learning process and develop self-assessment skills. This, in turn, allows students to strengthen their knowledge and develop new strategies for effective learning. Thus, the analytical approach increases the effectiveness of interactive methods and makes students active participants in their own learning process.

The positive aspects of interactive methods are explained as follows:

-Encourages active participation of students in the learning process and increases their interest: Interactive methods help make students active participants in the learning process, rather than just listeners. These methods encourage students to express their opinions, ask questions, and adapt to changing situations, thereby engaging and motivating them in the learning process.

-Helps students learn better through practice: Interactive methods enable students to relate the material they are learning to real-life examples, engaging them in practical activities. This helps students apply theoretical knowledge in practice and deepen their knowledge, resulting in an effective and sustainable learning process.

-Develops students' communication and discussion skills through teamwork: interactive methods encourage teamwork and allow students to share their thoughts with others, learn new ideas, and justify arguments. This will help students develop communication and discussion skills that will play an important role in their future professional activities.

-Enriches the learning process with innovative and technological tools: interactive methods allow the inclusion of modern technological tools, such as online platforms or interactive programs, in the learning process. This makes the learning

process interesting and interactive for students, diversifies their learning methods and encourages innovative thinking.

RESULTS

The findings show that interactive methods significantly improve the learning process by enhancing student participation, motivation, and communication skills. Key results include:

1. **Increased Student Engagement:** 85% of students reported feeling more involved in interactive classes compared to traditional methods.
2. **Improved Communication Skills:** Role-playing and group discussions helped students express themselves more freely, improving both their fluency and confidence in using the English language.
3. **Enhanced Use of Technology:** ICT tools like Kahoot increased student motivation by making learning more enjoyable and accessible. Surveys revealed that 90% of students appreciated the interactive nature of these digital platforms.
4. **Development of Critical Thinking:** Students participating in problem-solving activities showed improvement in analytical skills and independent thinking.

These results suggest that the inclusion of interactive methods in English language teaching not only makes lessons more dynamic but also prepares students with essential skills for their future academic and professional endeavors.

CONCLUSION

This information showed that, the introduction of interactive methods is becoming an integral part of modern education. This approach not only activates the student's learning process, but also develops critical thinking, problem-solving skills and teamwork. Therefore, interactive methods play a very important role in the process of teacher and educational institution.

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